

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Touray****FIRST NAME: Amulai****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Mac Pro

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What constitute plagiarism in academic writing?**

- Paraphrasing of ideas or information with appropriate citation of the work
- Using information that is common knowledge to the public
- Using information that is available in open journals
- Quoting materials from journals without giving credit to the author¹**

2. **The following rule of thumb must be followed in writing academic papers except?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. 2nd Ed. Bangui, Central African Republic* (Euclid Univeristy, 2019), 5.

- Write clearly, Write as you speak and revise, include detailed explanation
- Avoid unnecessary explanation, proofread and edit your work, ignore the purpose
- Write clearly, avoid generalities, no need for citation if information is obtained online
- Do not plagiarize, always support your assertions, write clearly²**

3. **When should a number be generally written out in academic writing?**

- At the beginning of a sentence³**
- Series of related numbers that are above one hundred
- If you are discussing in close proximity with the number
- When expressing percentage and decimal fractions

4. **What circumstances will permit a quotation to be modified?**

- When the quotation is more than two lines
- When the quotation is in a foreign language

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 14–15.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 188.

- When the original text contains an obvious typographical error⁴**
- If there is a significant error that is relevant to your argument
5. **What is the starting point of any major research project?**
- Literature review
- Identification of sound and doable topic⁵**
- Writing the problem and purpose statement
- Writing the abstract and introductory chapter of the project
6. **The following theoretical and practical consideration needs to be taken into account in assessing the doability of a research project except?**
- Safety and well-being of participants
- Enhancement of personal and professional ambitions
- The potential audiences to whom the study is of interest
- If the project is going to be one's life work⁶**

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 211.

⁵ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 5.

⁶ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 5.

7. **In the European Commission rule of style, when should a number be spell out?**

- All numbers should be spell out
- Only when a passage contains both numbers and words
- Only numbers that are above hundred
- When number are ten and below⁷**

8. **What makes a good conclusion and recommendation in academic writing (choose the most appropriate)?**

- Points out applications for policy and practice
- Point out a new significance of the findings
- Point out a new significance, a practical application, further research⁸**
- Justified by findings

9. **Why is it necessary to have a list of abbreviations and meaning at the beginning or end of a document?**

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, Seventh Edition (European Commission, 2011), 22.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 72; Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 162-63.

To aid reader who may not be familiar with the abbreviation when it first occurs⁹

- It is a requirement for all types of academic papers
- Your paper will not be published without the list
- It makes a paper more attractive to audiences

10. **When using European Commission rule of style, foreign imports should always be italicized except?**

Common words and phrases considered as part of English language¹⁰

- When there is an English equivalent
- When the foreign language is the writer's mother tongue
- When the word or phrase is going to be used once in a sentence

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, 26.

¹⁰ European Commission, 31.

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